

iQonic

IQONIC

**Innovative Strategies, Sensing and Process Chains for Increased
Quality, Reconfigurability and Recyclability of Manufacturing
Optoelectronics**

Deliverable 5.1

Feasible Defect Management Strategies in the IQONIC Use-Cases

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Executive Summary

This document reports the Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) within Work Package 5 (WP5) – Defect Life-Cycle Management, Disassembly and Remanufacturing of the project Innovative Strategies, Sensing and Process Chains for Increased Quality, Reconfigurability, and Recyclability of Manufacturing Optoelectronics (iQonic) funded by European Commission under the H2020-DT-FOF-03-2018 Innovative Manufacturing of Optoelectrical Parts, coordination and support topic under the grant agreement N° 820677.

D5.1 contains the identification of the several defect causes existing within the project use-cases linked to the respective feasible defect management actions that can be implemented to avoid these in-process defects to be propagated to the final product and lean towards Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) in multi-stage production systems. In the context of this deliverable, a “Use-case” is intended as the specific end- user business context in which the iQonic solutions will be validated. A common framework has been developed and the detailed information extracted from the project use-cases have been populated in a formal way. This work is preliminary and functional to the ongoing technical developments within WP5.

Abstract

The goal of the Task 5.1 (T5.1) – Evaluation of Functionalities and Downstream Strategies is to define, formalize and classify the feasible defect management strategies in the iQonic use-cases, where the developed solutions are going to be validated, in view of their technical and functional viability, residual value of the product and components and their impact on the productivity performance of the system, starting from the analysis of the most common defect causes and information about the product characteristics at different stages of the process-chain, to end with a complete description of the technical requirements for implementation, considering the required skills, tools and data communication infrastructure for each feasible defect management strategy.

Abbreviations

Table 1: Abbreviations

IQONIC	Innovative Strategies, Sensing and Process Chains for Increased Quality, Reconfigurability, and Recyclability of Manufacturing Optoelectronics
D5.1	Deliverable 5.1
WP5	Work Package 5
T5.1	Task 5.1
ZDM	Zero-Defect Manufacturing
COMD	Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage
COBD	Catastrophic Optical Bulk Damage
ESD	Electrostatic Discharge
EOS	Electrical Overstress
CPS	Cyber Physical System
PE	Prima Electronics
AL	Alpes
BW	Brighterwave
FI	Filar
HIL	HiLASE
N/A	Not Available

I Objective

The main objective of D5.1 within the project is to ensure a complete description and formalization of the existing defect types and the related feasible defect management strategies for the iQonic use-cases, namely Prima, Alpes, Filar and Brighterwave.

To reach the above-mentioned objective, the following actions have been carried out during T5.1:

- (i) Analysis of the most common defect causes in all use-cases;
- (ii) Analysis of product characteristics at different stages of the process chain;
- (iii) Identification of possible strategies:
 - a. Defect repair by downstream compensation;
 - b. Disassembly for direct reuse of components;
 - c. Disassembly for reuse through remanufacturing and regeneration.

A schematic view of actions is shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Actions of Task 5.1

As the final output, an entire description of the technical requirements for each possible defect management strategy is going to be achieved. The methodology followed in order to achieve the above-mentioned objective is described in *Chapter 2 (Methodology)*.

2 Methodology

The methodology followed on T5.1 includes identification, description and categorization of defect types in iQonic use-cases by also detailing the respective adopted inspection methods (e.g. visual inspection, testing, LIV (Light Current Voltage) characterization), their respective occurrence rates and feasible defect management actions. In order to achieve this goal, a table including the above mentioned information has been developed to retrieve this information from the project use-cases. The structure of this formalisms is given below in *Table 2*.

Table 2: Sample Table

<i>Defect type (code)</i>	<i>Defect Description</i>	<i>Defect Category</i>	<i>Stage Generated</i>	<i>Stage Inspected</i>	<i>Occurrence Rate</i>	<i>Feasible Actions</i>

Firstly, the most commonly faced defects, with respect to four use-cases, are going to be described more in detail, including the related defect pictures and technical definitions. Then, the procedure will eventually lead to the complete technical requirements in order to successfully perform each possible defect management strategy, including the information regarding implementation of strategy, the required skills, tools and data communication infrastructure. The Use-Cases, most commonly reported defects and their in-detail descriptions with respective defect pictures are given in the next chapter, *Chapter 3 (iQonic Use-Cases)*.

3 IQONIC Use-Cases

In this section, a closer look at each type of defect reported in all of the use-cases will be taken, including the definition of defects, possible causes of defects and defect pictures.

3.1 ALPES Use-Case

Alpes acts as an end-user of the iQonic platform, aiming at reducing their defects, increasing their yields, achieving faster and more accurate reconfiguration times, while exploring the reverse supply chain process to increase their sustainability. In order to achieve that, the primary objective of Alpes within Task 5.1 is to identify and explore the defects generated in manufacturing stages and implement a complementary defect management strategy.

The defects detected in the ALPES use-case is shown in *Table 3*.

Table 3: Defects in the ALPES Use-Case

Defect type (code)	Defect Description	Defect Category	Stage Generated	Stage Inspected	Occurrence Rate	Feasible Actions
AL01	Structural defect on chip; visible under microscope	Structural defect	Epitaxy or Front-end	Wafer validation / Mounting	Wafer and region dependent; range 1% - 50%	Scrap
AL02	Structural defect on chip; visible electrically	Structural defect	Epitaxy or Front-end	Testing	Percent range	Scrap
AL03	Structural defect on chip / wafer; visible after ALT	Structural defect	Epitaxy or Front-end	ALT testing	N/A	Scrap
AL04	Cleaving failure; resulting in beam obstruction or shingle passing through emission region	Structural defect	Chip cleaving	Facet inspection	Variable; ranging from 1% - 10%	Scrap
AL05	Dirt particle on facet in emission region	Cleanliness	Chip cleaving / mounting	Facet inspection	Percent range	Cleaning or Scrap
AL06	Coating failure (adhesion, contamination, homogeneity)	Structural defect	Facet coating	Facet inspection	Affects coating batches, relatively rare	Scrap
AL07	Device failure during testing	Device failure	Testing	Testing	Percent range	Scrap
AL08	Device off-spec	Off-spec	Design / Front-end	Testing	Only applies to small number of clients; can be as high as 50% or even higher	Re-use in other applications
AL09	Device becomes bi-mode	Device alteration	HHL packaging	Testing	2.5-5%	Replace chip; Re-use package

The comprehensive description of defects reported in *Table 3* for Alpes Use-Case is given in the next section.

Figure 2: Defects of Epitaxial Growth Attributed to Surface Contamination

Figure 3: Defects of Epitaxial Growth Attributed to Surface Contamination (Side View)

Figure 3 shows the same defect as shown in Figure 2, but from the side view. The crystal has been cleaved along the active region. The defects manifests as bumps or even cavities along the waveguide.

Some defects from device fabrication can be detected by visual inspection after reception of the wafers from the sub-contractor. *Figure 2* and *Figure 3* show epitaxial growth defects that were attributed to a surface contamination of the sample prior to lateral regrowth (selective epitaxial regrowth of InP in MOCVD). The defects align with the position of the waveguide which distinguishes them from random growth defects (with no influence on device behaviour) that are randomly scattered across the wafer surface with larger densities close to the border of the wafer. As *Figure 3* shows, the defects are manifested through bumps or even cavities along the waveguide. In this particular case the defects resulted in heavily increased waveguide losses and thus devices that showed no electrical damage, but the devices were just not lasing.

Another structural defect that unfortunately occurs on a regular basis and that can easily be identified after cleaving of the device facet is shown in *Figure 4*. In that case, the SiN_x hard mask detached during the processing step of epitaxial lateral regrowth in a MOCVD reactor at high temperature. This is a selective epitaxial regrowth with insulating material (InP:Fe). The top of the waveguide that was supposed to be protected by a layer of silicon nitride was overgrown with insulating InP:Fe. As a consequence, no current can be injected into the device.

Figure 4: Waveguide Overgrown with Semi-Insulating InP:Fe.

The epitaxial growth defects shown above affect typically only parts of the wafer. While the devices affected by the defects have absolutely no way of being re-worked and therefore are scrap, devices from other parts of the wafer can be perfectly fine. However, it is important to detect the presence of these defects as early as possible in order to remove them from the “standard” production flow and therefore unnecessary use resources (material, mounting and testing time).

AL02 – Structural Defect Visible Electrically

These are defects that can be detected as soon as electrical testing of the device is possible. In the case of QC technology (facet-emitters, inherently) this testing cannot be performed on a wafer level, but only once bars have been cleaved. In Alpes, bar-testing is not performed on all wafers but only on specific occasions (low yield processes).

Figure 5: LIV characteristic of a faulty, non-working device (first test).

AL03 – Lifetime Affecting Defect

In Alpes, ALT setup is being constructed currently. So far, there is no data regarding ALT testing available. Once the setup will be running (June 2020) 16 samples will be aged at 60-80°C for 1-2 weeks. Overall statistics will yield information on expected MTTF for the processed wafers where the “failure” is a complete device failure (electrical). Secondary “failures” will include change of device performance data (emission power and spectral position/purity). However, for the secondary failures will only be considered in a second step.

Figure 6: Deep structural defect that "burned-through" during ALT testing

Figure 7: "Shingle" Crossing Device Facet

Figure 8: Scribing Error

Defects occurring during cleaving of the devices are shown in *Figure 7* and *Figure 8*. Contrary to silicon wafers in the chip industry no dicing with diamond saw is performed. The crystal dies are cleaved along crystallographic planes by applying structural defects at the surface using a diamond scribe and then applying pressure to break the sample. "Shingles" and structural defects are not considered "eliminator" if the zones are away from the emitting zone of the device.

Figure 9: Dirt Particle on Device Facet (Non-Critical if no coating is to be deposited)

Figure 10: Deposition of Unknown Material on Device Facet

Dirt particles on a device facet is not considered critical as long as the particle is away from the emitting zone of the device. In case a particle is close to the emitting zone some cleaning can be performed using a flow of nitrogen gas. Other defects like shown in *Figure 10* are “terminal” and devices have to be scrapped.

Figure 11: Failure of AR-Coating

Figure 12: Detachment of (Metallic) HR-Coating

Coating is performed typically after COS mounting because the dielectric coatings used for mid-infrared devices do not reliably stand the high temperature used for COS mounting. Coating failures can affect whole batches (contamination of the evaporation chamber, the crucibles or the material) or single devices (typically contamination of device facet). Devices with coating failures are scrapped as no way of removing the coating without affecting the reliability of the device is known.

AL07 – Device Failure During Testing

Figure 13: Failed Device Plot During Testing

All devices that Alpes sell are tested on the characterization stations. Device failure during testing can be due to structural problems of the device as well as operator error. Devices that fail during testing cannot be repaired and therefore are scrapped together with the AlN sub-mount.

AL08 – Off-Spec Device

Figure 14: Device that does not meet wavelength specifications (shown as red vertical bars) at given operating point

For DFB laser specifications include typically temperature operating range, wavelength tuning, emission power, device dissipation (without and including TEC element). Devices that do not satisfy the specs of a specific client can be perfectly suitable for another client.

AL09 – Degradation of Spectral Purity After Packaging

Figure 15: Alteration of Spectral Purity: Device becomes bi-mode after packaging

Alpes' DFB products need to be spectrally clean in order to be useable for spectroscopic measurements. Sometimes, devices that are perfectly mono-mode (SMR > 24dB) prior to packaging become bi-mode after packaging. Because the housing and parts for the packaging are expensive, in that case, the packages are reworked. The old laser and sub-mount are removed and another device with similar performances is mounted again.

3.2 PRIMA Use-Case

In Prima Electro (PE) use-case, multiemitter laser diodes will be assembled in order to achieve the required power. Diodes must satisfy the challenging characteristics of emitted power, wall plug efficiency, laser beam quality and diode life under critical operating conditions. Considering the 60% of the total cost of laser comes from diode manufacturing processes, the diode laser manufacturing process is highly influential from economical point of view.

Since the laser source manufacturing chain of Prima is highly vertically integrated, the product and process controls play a crucial role in the context of ZDM. In order to avoid possible challenges in the future and fulfil the goals of Prima within WP5 of iQonic, such as introducing a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) for the optimal binning of diodes, selection of classified components for assembly, implementation of a feed-forward control strategy for assemble strategy adaptation; and from more general point of view, improvement on defect repair, disassembly, remanufacturing phases and reuse of the components, the definitions of commonly faced defects and their management strategies are very important.

The defect types identified in the PRIMA use-case are reported in *Table 4*.

Table 4: Defects in the PRIMA Use-Case

Defect type (code)	Defect Description	Defect Category	Stage Generated	Stage Inspected	Occurrence Rate	Feasible Actions
PE01	Contamination of the die facet	Surface defect	All (back end)	Visual inspect	4%	Scrap
PE02	Cracking	Cleavage defect	Cleavage	Visual inspect	3%	Scrap
PE03	Metal on ridge	Surface defect	Cleavage	Visual inspect	1%	Scrap
PE04	Coating	Surface defect	Coating	Visual inspect	0.02%	Scrap
PE05	Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage	Surface defect	Testing	Visual inspect	2%	Scrap
PE06	Mounting	Mechanical alignment	Die attach	Visual inspect	1%	Scrap or Recycle ('b' spec)
PE07	Power Voltage Performance	Parametric	Testing	Testing	7%	Scrap or Recycle ('b' spec)
PE08	Wavelength	Parametric	Testing	Testing	Not yet implemented	Scrap or Recycle ('b' spec)
PE09	Burn In Fail	Reliability	Stress Test	Reliability	12%	Scrap

CoC Process Description

The process description of Chip-on-Carrier (CoC) and commonly faced defects will be explained in this section.

Figure 16: CoC Process Description

The CoC Testing and PASS/FAIL Criteria is explained in *Figure 16*. Defects from device fabrication must be detected according to input quality assessment requirements of the back-end departments, namely the visual inspection, testing and reliability department. Visual inspection is in charge of detecting the morphology defects, according to the following categories:

- Contamination of the die facet
- Cracking
- Metal on ridge
- Coating
- Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage
- Mounting

Testing department will detect parts not compliant to the electro-optical specifications; most important parameters are:

- Power Voltage Performance
- Wavelength

Reliability department is in charge to assess the device robustness, removing the maverick and prevent infant failure issues in the final product: in addition to the parametric measurements, will define:

- Burn In fail

Parts which parameters variation during stress (Burn in) are wider than specified; those parts are rejected as not enough robust and therefore its expectation of lifetime is not compliant to the specs.

CoC Testing PASS/FAIL Criteria

In this section, the criteria followed by Prima in order to detect the failure and apply the most feasible defect management strategy is going to be further evaluated. CoC Failure Analysis is shown in *Figure 17*.

Figure 17: CoC Failure Analysis

After CoC manufacturing is performed, the properties tested for each diode are namely contamination, reliability, power and wavelength.

- Contamination: There are two main sources reported by Prima causing contamination on CoC, coating and handling operations. Dirt and dust remaining on CoC is causing this issue as well as metal residues. The action taken by Prima in this case is scrapping the component.
- Reliability: Catastrophic Optical Bulk Damage (COBD), Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage (COMD), Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) and Electrical Overstress (EOS) are reported as main sources of failure about CoC Reliability.

COMD failure is commonly faced in semiconductor lasers. If semiconductor is overloaded by exceeded power density or absorption of energy, the facet of laser gets damaged. Crystal defects, contamination and oxidation are the triggering factors of COMD.

Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) is the instantaneous electricity flow between two charged materials. The flow can even occasionally create a visible spark. However, also in less dramatic forms of ESD in which the phenomenon is not visible, the damage left on sensitive electronic devices can be crucial.

Electrical Overstress (EOS) in semiconductors increases the temperature of a local area that can lead to changing the structure of layers, even melts the layer. This significantly shortens the lifetime of the product.

All of these failure causes eventually lead to scrapping of component.

- Power: The previously explained failure modes in 'Reliability' have nonnegligible connection with power. In addition to that, some parametric failures are reported by Prima related to wafer part, such as wafer inhomogeneities and wafer processing. If the CoC fails in power test and parametric failure has been found out, the defect management strategy suggests recycling within the WP5 of iQonic.
- Wavelength: The wavelength failure is usually caused by the failure of a parameter and with recycling, the problem can be solved.

In the next section, multiemitter process description will be given and PASS/FAIL criteria will be explained more in detail for scrapping and recycling of assembled components.

Multimitter Process Description

Figure 18: Multimitter Process Description

Figure 18 describes the multimitter assembly process in Prima Use-Case. After assembly, the following parameters are tested for each multimitter;

- Power
- Reliability
- CoC soldering

When the test fails, a failure analysis examines the root cause and the possibility to recycle or scrap the multimitter.

Multimitter Testing and PASS/FAIL Criteria

Figure 19: Multimitter Testing and Failure Analysis for Recycling

Figure 19 shows the multimitter testing and failure analysis for recycling of failed parts. Three main solutions are proposed for three commonly faced failure sources: CoC failure, ferrule failure and optics misalignments.

In case of CoC failures, CoC is replaced through recycling procedure. Ferrule failures are primarily caused by fiber contamination and ferrule out of specifications. Ferrule replacement is required in that case to avoid scrapping the multiemitter. Lastly, optical misalignments can be repaired by realignment.

Figure 20: Multiemitter Testing and Failure Analysis for Scrap

Figure 20 shows the multiemitter testing and failure analysis for scrapping. In case of a failure repeating itself, e.g. CoC not properly soldered more than once or ferrule fails more than once and realignment is no further possible, in the power test or monitoring multiemitter CoC soldering parameters, the part is scrapped.

The next section in this chapter contains the pictures and in-depth description of defects reported in Table 4 for Prima Use-Case.

Figure 21: Contamination of the Die Facet

Typical example of facet contamination, as detected by the visual inspection is reported in *Figure 21*; contamination might be originated by dirt, or semiconductor particles. Whether this contamination is in the critical area, i.e. area in which optical density is high, parts have to be rejected since potentially not robust, or optical properties might be somehow affected.

PE02 – Cracking

Figure 22: Cracking

Figure 22 shows an example of device cracking. This semiconductor brake can be originated during device bar cleaving, or - like the example shown by the picture - by the device dicing (also called singulation, which separates device from the bars). Each brake not terminated originates a device rejected by the visual inspection. According to product specs, criteria might vary, e.g. some product can accept brakes far from the electrical/optical active region.

PE03 – Metal on Ridge

Figure 23: Metal on Ridge

Figure 23 shows an example of metal issue. During the bar scribing process, which creates the laser diode facets, metal has to be separated by the scribing process avoiding any unwanted metal particle in front of the facet itself. Sometimes metal reaches out from the top ‘p’ side metal toward the facet, leading to a potentially corrupted emitted beam, or even worst overheating since photons absorption, and therefore compromising expected device lifetime. Parts with metal detected in the critical area have to be rejected by the visual inspection procedure.

Figure 24: Coating

Figure 24 shows an example of coating issue. During the coating process, devices at left and right side of the bar will be not correctly coated since shadow effect introduced by the jig shape. Device are normally removed automatically from the population (at bar testing stage) but there are few possibilities of detecting device with partial coating since bar mispositioned in the coating jig. Those devices have to be rejected, since coating is also ensuring facet passivation and therefore critically contributing to long term reliability.

PE05 – Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage (COMD)

Figure 25: Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage (COMD)

COMD is a catastrophic damage effect typical of Al-containing active layers of semiconductor lasers. Process is triggered by the Al compounds which are extremely reactive to oxygen, creating a native oxidation process during facet cleavage. This oxidation is non-radiatively absorbing photons, increasing locally the facet temperature, which furthermore increase optical absorption (due to bandgap thermal shrinkage phenomena) which leads to a catastrophic effect, with temperature rising in sub-microsecond scale up to the semiconductor melting point.

Device which facet passivation was not perfect, or with a residual defect rates too high, will show this feature after testing (see *Figure 25*), and should be rejected since performances and reliability can be strongly affected.

PE06 – Mounting

Figure 26: Mounting

Devices needs a very precise positioning on the carrier during the die attach: proper soldering ensure a good thermal dissipation (including facet temperature) together with not interfering with emitted optical beam. Visual inspection will detect whether device is assembled too much protruding from the carrier (*positive overhang*, affecting thermal dissipation, like in *Figure 26*) or in the opposite direction (*negative overhang*, which would affect optical beam quality).

Figure 27: Example of Power Fail

Devices are screened at bar level in terms of optical performances. *Figure 27* shows an example of power fail devices, which are emitting a lower power since technological problems: high threshold current indicates higher cavity losses (crystal defects, or damage in the facet mirror) or lower gain (active material issues or not ideal current injection). At bar level, device is not able to dissipate power: hence the test is performed at relatively low current (2 – 4 amp maximum) and in a very short pulsed condition (typ. 4 μ s, 0.1% duty cycle).

PE09 – Burn In Fail

Figure 28: Example of Burn In Fail: Pre-burn in and Post-burn in (red curve) are compared for the same device, fail at test

Devices are screened at Chip on Carrier (CoC) level in terms of device robustness. *Figure 28* shows an example of burn in fail device, which are emitting a lower power since failure during stress test (Burn in).

Burn In procedure has to be carefully defined during product development and is a mandatory need of diode laser technology. Part of the diode population might have intrinsic defects not detectable at $t = 0$ from the optical performances. It is therefore necessary to perform a stress test which activates defects, leading eventually to device failure. Comparing the power variation pre and post stress test, product engineer can define a proper mask criterion which will effectively detect maverick devices, removing weak parts from population, without affecting expected lifetime of good parts.

3.3 FILAR Use-Case

The Filar use-case is divided into two sub use-cases by the consortium members, namely Sub Use-Case 3A and Sub Use-Case 3B (see D2.4). Sub Use-Case 3A mainly focuses on the challenges related to monitoring, control and improvement of the process chain at Filar. Instead, Sub Use-Case 3B focuses more on the manufacturing of a potentially new product in Filar product portfolio, namely the thin-disk in cooperation with HiLASE. The introduction and development of a completely new product and related process-chain is the target objective of Sub Use-Case 3B.

3.3.1 FILAR Sub Use-Case 3A

Filar Sub Use-Case 3A, aims to improve the most critical opto-mechanical cutting, i.e. Ultrasound Machining (USM), the adoption of robotics handling to improve the controllability of the polishing process and improvement of coating and quality control stages that are positioned downstream to the crystal growth process are addressed. Hence, the defect identification and defect management actions have a significant impact.

The defects detected in the FILAR Sub Use-Case 3A is shown in *Table 5*.

Table 5: Defects in the FILAR Sub Use-Case 3A

Defect type (code)	Defect Description	Defect Category	Stage Generated	Stage Inspected	Occurrence Rate	Feasible Actions
FI01	Microfractures in the sonotrode given by thermal stress Tip not perfectly in axis	Alignment between the tip and the boule	Tip preparation	Tip preparation	35%	An analog dial gauge is used to control the correct position
FI02	Cracks in the junction	Quality of the welding between the tip and the sonotrode	Tip preparation	Tip preparation, drilling process	25%	Induction welding process
FI03	Not uniformity of the barrel edge	Penetration speed and progression	Drilling process	Drilling process	20%	The process needs more frequency amplitude
FI04	Crystal stressing	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
FI05	Uneven material consumption	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

The next section describes particular defects given above in *Table 5* for Filar Sub Use-Case 3A.

Figure 29: Tip not Perfectly in Axis

Welding quality influences the vibration transmission from the ultrasonic generator to the tip. The welding is performed by an acetylene torch. The possible issues related to the process are reported as:

- (i) Microfractures in the sonotrode given by thermal stress
- (ii) Tip not perfectly in axis

In order to precisely align the tip on the axis, three control screws are used to direct the sonotrode to be perfectly parallel to the air levitated cart on rail on which the entire machine moves. An analog dial gauge is used to control the correct position. Moreover, due to the thermal stress during the welding process, possible microfractures in the sonotrode can be observed.

FI02 – Cracks in the Junction

Figure 30: Cracks in the Junction

Another thermal effect of the welding process, combined with sudden drop of penetration speed to zero, is reported as cracks in the junction tip, as shown in *Figure 30*. This phenomenon strongly affects the quality of the welding between the tip and the sonotrode.

FI03 – Non-Uniformity of the Barrel Edge

The parameters that can be controlled in real-time to influence the process speed, which is checked by an analog range finder, are:

- (i) Amplitude of vibrations
- (ii) Abrasive material concentration
- (iii) Pressure of the tip on the crystal (using weights)

Unexpected situations due to the penetration speed are reported as:

- 1) If the penetration speed *slows down*:
 - a. the abrasive powder concentration decreases
 - b. the process requires more amplitude
 - c. the tip shortens too much
 - d. the suction pump does not work (i.e. plugged tube)
 - e. weight becomes not enough to pull the cart

- 2) If the penetration speed suddenly *goes to zero*:
 - a. possible tip occlusion caused by the abrasive powder
 - b. ultrasound frequency problems occur
 - c. cracks in the junction tip - sonotrode occur

Frequency is controlled by a software. However, when the process requires more frequency amplitude, as reported in case of penetration speed slows down, non-uniformity of the barrel edge can be observed.

FI04 – Crystal Stressing

After the drilling, the rod goes in the centerless grinding machine (see *Figure 31*) to take a perfectly cylindrical shape. This process stresses the crystal, affecting its beam shape, as shown in *Figure 32*. Alexandrite, more than other crystals, suffers from this phenomenon.

Figure 31: Centerless Grinding Machine

Figure 32: Crystal Stressing

Figure 33: Rod Lapping

Lapping jigs used in Filar use-case have three control screws used to orientate the rod inside (with an autocollimator) and three locking screws with springs. During the process, the jigs can freely rotate resting in the roller yokes but sometimes the rotation is not constant and uneven material consumption can be observed.

3.3.2 FILAR Sub Use-Case 3B

The Filar Sub Use-Case 3B, executed in cooperation with HiLASE, focused on a thin-disk laser bonding to a heat sink. The bonding process is nowadays done manually. The interest of HiLASE is to develop more automated process and to implement essential defects detection during the bonding process which will prevent their appearance.

The defects in Filar Sub Use-Case 3B use-case are shown in *Table 6*.

Table 6: Defects in Filar Sub Use-Case 3B

Defect type (code)	Defect Description	Defect Category	Stage Generated	Stage Inspected	Occurrence Rate	Feasible Actions
HIL01	Thin-disk surface is out of specification	Surface defect	Material preparation	Before bonding	N/A	Scrap /re-polishing
HIL02	The heat sink roughness is out of specification	Surface defect	Material preparation	Before bonding	N/A	Re-polishing
HIL03	Voids/non-uniform HR and AR coatings on thin disk	Surface defect	Material preparation	Before bonding	N/A	Scrap
HIL04	Particle contamination of thin-disk or heat sink surface	Surface defect	Material preparation	Before bonding	N/A	Cleaning/Scrap
HIL05	Non-uniform thickness of adhesive layer	Structural defect	During the bonding	After bonding	N/A	Thin disk-scrap/ heat sink recycling
HIL06	Bubbles and voids in adhesive layer	Structural defect	During the bonding	After bonding	N/A	Thin disk-scrap/ heat sink recycling
HIL07	Thin disk- heat sink misalignment	Structural defect	During the bonding	After bonding	N/A	Thin disk-scrap/ heat sink recycling
HIL08	Thin disk is bended after bonding	Structural defect	During the bonding	After bonding	N/A	Thin disk-scrap/ heat sink recycling
HIL09	Thin-disk module performance	Structural defect	After bonding	Testing	N/A	Thin disk-scrap/ heat sink recycling

The commonly faced defects reported by Filar Sub Use-Case 3B that are reported in *Table 6* are elaborated in the next section.

Defects Definitions and Pictures in FILAR Sub Use-Case 3B

HIL01 – Thin Disk Surface Out of Specification

These defects influence future performance and quality of the thin disk module. Critical are structural defects on the HR-coated disk side which can later influence the bonding procedure itself. Such defects like micro-cracks, scratches, peaks, valleys, or high surface roughness in general prevent from high quality bonding and larger defects with fatal consequences for the disk can propagate from the originally small defects. Micro-cracks are not acceptable at all, other kind of the mentioned defects over the surface must be limited. Requested micro-roughness should be in average $R_a \ll 1$ nm, peak-to-valley inside working area of the disk should be also < 1 nm. Because of large disk size, the roughness is measured randomly in several spots on the disk and evaluated statistically.

Figure 34: Microscope picture showing a micro-crack propagating from a crystal edge (view from the facet)

Other group of defects are issues related to overall flatness. Unlike the microstructural defects, the flatness is measured over full aperture of the laser disk since lower resolution is required. It is shown like a deviation from an ideally flat surface in nanometers or like a multiple of λ , i.e. probe laser wavelength. Flatness in working area (approximate diameter 5 mm in the disk center) should not exceed $\lambda/8$ before bonding (< 100 nm), tolerance at the disk edge is higher. Low flatness negatively influences performance of the disk module from point of view of laser beam quality.

Figure 35: Examples of unacceptable flatness of thin disks measured by an interferometer (peaks and valleys out of specs)

All disk surface defects are analyzed before the bonding. Some of them can be repaired by re-polishing, some of them (cracks) cannot be repaired.

Figure 36: Image of well-polished thin disk surface before bonding. Working area in the disk center shows deviations < 5 nm

HIL02 - Heatsink Surface Out of Specification

Heatsink surface defects and their characterization are similar to thin disk (laser crystal) surface analysis, including limits on micro-roughness (Ra, scratch-digs) and surface flatness. SiC or diamond heatsink is usually very hard and reaching of low roughness is difficult (see fig.), for metallic heatsinks like copper is difficult to reach good flatness (soft material). Analysis must be done before the bonding; defective pieces can be re-polished. High Ra value can prevent reaching of high bonding force, low flatness can bend the thin disk.

Figure 37: Micro-roughness measurement of a heatsink - high resolution image measured by interferometer (80 x 80 um). Unacceptable digs are obvious on the figure

Figure 38: Scratches on surface of a metallic heatsink caused by improper handling during bonding procedure

HIL03 – Voids/Non-Uniform HR and AR coatings on Thin-Disk

Voids and non-uniform coatings on the thin disk have similar effect on the bonding procedure like out-of-spec roughness of the disk or heatsink surface. The defects come from imperfections during ion beam sputtering of dielectric layers. Voids in the coating can be initiated by surface defects of a thin disk, particles on the disk not removed during the disk cleaning or creation of particle clusters during the material deposition, non-uniformity come for example from wrong handling, geometry and other parameters of the sputtering process. This kind of defects cannot be repaired at all.

Quality of HR coating is critical for the quality of bonding procedure (it is a part of the bonding layer), however, both AR and HR coatings influence performance and lifetime of the module.

Figure 39: Microscopic image of unacceptable voids in HR coating (black dots)

HIL04 - Particle Contamination of Thin-Disk or Heat Sink Surface

Free particles on surfaces of laser disk or a heat sink have similar effect on thin disk bonding like surface or coating defects but usually come from material storage and handling. Besides effects on quality of the bonding, dust particles absorb laser radiation, initiate failures of HR and AR coatings, and finally cause catastrophic failure of the module. After pre-assembling inspection can be the components carefully cleaned (ultrasonic cleaner), however, too high contamination is impossible to be cleaned and may cause permanent damage on the components.

Figure 40: Microscopic images of dust particles on the disk surface

HIL05 - Non-Uniform Thickness of Adhesive Layer

Non-uniform thickness of adhesives leads to inhomogeneous heat extraction and lower performance of the module. Inhomogeneous temperature distribution also deteriorates laser beam quality. Excess of epoxy as shown in the figure increases absorption of radially propagating photons and finally can lead to catastrophic failure of the module. This kind of defect is irreparable.

Figure 41: Inhomogeneous layer of epoxy (left), excess of epoxy increasing photon absorption at a disk edge

HIL06 - Bubbles and Voids in Adhesive Layer

Bubbles or voids in the epoxy layer lead to worse cooling of the module and lower laser performance or module lifetime. Creation of the defect is influenced by viscosity and thickness of the layer. Voids in the layer can grow during laser operation and lead to thin disk delamination and catastrophic failure. This kind of defects is irreparable.

Figure 42: Microscopic image of bubbles in epoxy layer

Figure 43: Voids in the adhesive layer around disk edges (brighter areas) and close to a disk center (right figure)

Figure 44: Delamination and catastrophic failure of the thin disk caused by defects in adhesive layer

HIL07 – Thin-Disk Misalignment

Thin disk misalignment is a less serious geometrical defect which can affect homogeneity of temperature distribution and module performance. Proper alignment must be done before epoxy curing during the bonding procedure, later is the defect irreparable.

Figure 45: Image of misaligned Yb:YAG thin disk bonded to a SiC heat sink

HIL08 – Thin-Disk is Bended After Bonding

Even perfectly flat heat sink and thin disk can result in deterioration of thin disk flatness with serious consequence in thin disk performance. Figure shows bending of a thin disk module after epoxy curing. Critical for the module performance is residual aspherical deformation which cannot be compensated by construction of a laser system. Creation of the defect is determined by handling and tools used during the bonding procedure. After epoxy curing is the defect irreparable.

Figure 46: Interferometric image of a bonded thin disk module surface. Total surface flatness (left), and flatness after subtracting spherically symmetrical deformation (right), which is critical

HIL09 – Thin-disk Module Performance

Final tests of the module are performed in a simple laser cavity with measurement of static and dynamical bending of the thin disk under different operating conditions. Other measured parameters are surface temperature distribution, laser beam profile, and output power. Since the pumped area of a thin disk shows higher temperature than surroundings, disk modules are bending like the sketch in a *Figure 46*. Following figures show disk behavior during the burn-in tests like the growth of defect size after warming-up cycles, total optical path difference measured in x and y direction under different operating conditions (consequence of disk flatness), disk surface temperature, and finally performance of laser test bench with degradation of beam profile by aspherical disk deformation at higher operating temperatures. Only modules passing the test cycles repeatedly can be consigned.

Figure 47: Dynamical bending of a thin disk caused by thermal expansion of a pumped area

Figure 48: Growth of defect size after warming-up cycles during burn-in tests

Figure 49: Optical path difference in x and y direction for different pump powers and lasing/non-lasing conditions (left); measurement of disk surface temperature by a thermal camera for 2 different pump wavelengths and 2 different disk modules (right)

Pump power and Intensity		Pump wavelength [W]	
		940 nm	969 nm
105 W 1.7 kW/cm ²	Beam profile		
	Output power [W]	23	29
190 W 3.1 kW/cm ²	Beam profile		
	Output power [W]	55	65
280 W 4.6 kW/cm ²	Beam profile		
	Output power [W]	90	104
320 W 5.2 kW/cm ²	Beam profile	NA	
	Output power [W]	-	107
360 W 5.9 kW/cm ²	Beam profile	NA	
	Output power [W]	-	132

Figure 50: Performance test of a thin disk module for 2 different pump wavelengths (940 and 969 nm). Output power and spatial mode profile are recorded. In this case is the module acceptable up to 50 W.

3.4 BRIGHTERWAVE Use-Case

The Brighterwave use-case investigates how to define and scale up a suitable process chain in order to be able to produce two targeted products from Brighterwave portfolio with higher production rates. During WP5, a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) for the proper re-use of discarded components for other high-value added applications will be developed for Brighterwave. Therefore, in order to properly evaluate the reasoning of discarded components, the defect types and their clear definitions have to be managed first.

The defects detected in the BRIGHTERWAVE use-case is shown in *Table 7*.

Table 7: Defects in the BRIGHTERWAVE Use-Case

Defect type (code)	Defect Description	Defect Category	Stage Generated	Stage Inspected	Inspection method	Occurrence Rate	Feasible Actions
BW01	Contamination of the laser diode facet	Surface defect	Front-end (supplier)	Front-end	Optical/Visual	1% - 3%	Scrap
BW02	Other surface defect in the laser diode	Surface defect	Front-end (supplier)	Front-end	Optical/Visual	1% - 3%	Scrap / Use for the modules with reduced performance
BW03	Internal defect in the laser diode	Internal defect	Front-end (supplier)	Front-end	Burn-in	1% - 2%	Scrap
BW04	Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage	Surface defect	In operation	Packaging	Optical/Visual	1% - 5%	Scrap
BW05	Contamination of the nonlinear crystal facet	Surface defect	Front-end (supplier)	Incoming quality inspection at Brighterwave	Optical/Visual	1% - 3%	Scrap
BW06	Internal defect in the nonlinear crystal	Internal defect	Front-end (supplier)	Incoming quality inspection at Brighterwave	Optical/Visual	2% - 5%	Scrap / Use for the modules with reduced performance
BW07	Misalignment	Performance	Packaging	Packaging	LIV (light-current-voltage) characterization	2% - 15%	Scrap / Use for the modules with reduced performance
BW08	Other packaging defect	Performance	Packaging	Packaging	LIV (light-current-voltage) characterization	1% - 5%	Scrap / Use for the modules with reduced performance

The upcoming section contains information related to defect types reported in *Table 7* for Brighterwave Use-Case.

Defects Definitions and Pictures in Brighterwave Use-Case

BW04 – Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage (COMD)

Figure 51: Typical Image of the Laser Facet Failed due to Catastrophic Optical Mirror Damage (COMD)

BW05 – Contamination of the Non-Linear Crystal Facet

Figure 52: Microscope picture showing defects at the crystal facet (view from the facet)

Defects at the crystal facet are important only when they are at the waveguide position or close to the waveguide. The waveguide is not shown in *Figure 52*.

BW06 – Internal Defect in the Non-Linear Crystal

Figure 53: Microscope picture showing the waveguide and two internal defects in non-linear crystal (top-view image)

Internal defect at the waveguide position can cause considerable optical losses and deteriorate device operation, whereas defect outside the waveguide position (at distance $> 20\mu\text{m}$) is not important.

4 Conclusions and Next Steps

In this deliverable (D5.1), the most common defects faced in four use-cases are analyzed in detail. For the identified, categorized and described defects, feasible defect management strategies pursuant to zero-defect manufacturing (ZDM) are specified and evaluated. As a next step in Task 5.1, for each feasible defect management strategy, a complete description of the technical requirements for implementation will be detailed and formalized, considering the required skills, tools and data communication infrastructure. Later on, to continue with Task 5.2 - Defect Severity and Decision Support for Optimum Response to Defects, the optimization of process chains operations against defect management strategies will be performed. The described defects in Task 5.1 for all use-cases will be analyzed and classified in terms of defect severity, occurrence and impact on involved process chain and production. In order to incorporate autonomous and hierarchical decision support with respect to provided recommendations combining product monitoring models and data analytics from heterogeneous sources, a Decision Support System (DSS) will be designed. The DSS will encompass a rule-based engine, for deciding the strategy(ies) to be activated, therefore, semantic rules will be defined along with conditions for the activation of each one of the IQONIC intertwined strategies: Diagnose, Predict, Adjust, Prevent, Detect, Sustain, Redesign and Manage.

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